

In Search of the Lost Author: A Stylometric Analysis of 185 Romanian Novels Published Between 1850-1950

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OUTLINE

1. Testing the performance of StyloR package on a collection of Romanian novels already included in corpora HAI-RO, ELTeC, POP-LITE

2. Checking stylistic solidarities:
 - 2.1 novel subgenres (settings: ClassicDelta vs. CosineDelta vs. no sampling)
 - 2.2. authorship attribution (settings: ClassicDelta vs. Canberra vs. sampling)
 - 2.3. modernization stages of Romanian language (settings: ClassicDelta vs. CosineDelta vs. no sampling)
to be determined

3. Discussion of StyloR data vs. state-of-the-art approaches:
 - 3.1.literary theory approaches to novel subgenres (e.g. DCRR 2007, monographs, etc.)
 - 3.2. literary history approaches to anonymous authors (DGLR 2016, monographs, etc.)
 - 3.3. language and literary history approaches to periodization (Şuteu 1981, Şuteu 1976, Hristea 1981, Stan 2011, Călinescu 1982 etc.)

Testing the performance of StyloR on Romanian

1. Stylometrics and StyloR – short description of the package

- What is stylometry? (Wincenty Lutosławski – chronology of Plato's writings based on discourse analysis)
- Recent developments in computational literary studies (Donovan, Zadworna-Fjellestad și Lundén 2008, Juola 2008, Dinu, Dinu și Popescu 2008, Stamatatos 2009, Vickers 2011, Herrmann, Van Dalen-Oskam, and Schöch 2015, Teodorescu & Bolea 2018, Primorac et al. 2023):
 - *Authorship attribution* for the Gospels and some of Shakespeare's, Marlowe's, J.K. Rowling's, Brontë Sisters' works, and many others
 - *Collaborative authorship*
- What is StyloR (options, settings) = there are no settings yet for Romanian language (lack of machine-readable Romanian literary corpora?)

<https://cran.r-project.org/web/packages/stylo/index.html> (Eder, Rybicki și Kestemont, 2016)

INPUT & LANGUAGE

FEATURES

STATISTICS

SAMPLING

OUTPUT

INPUT:

plain text

xml

xml (plays)

xml (no titles)

html

LANGUAGE:

English

English (contr.)

English (ALL)

Latin

Latin (u/v > u)

Polish

Hungarian

French

Italian

Spanish

Dutch

German

CJK

Other

Native encoding

OK

TIME for a DISCLAIMER

If we fail to provide answers, it's not because of
StyloR;
it's because we should have remained literary
historians.

Methodological principles:

A. Cluster Analysis (CA): interrogate the collection by applying a general parametric (say, Classic Delta, 100 MFW etc.); checking the writers whose works group perfectly and then list them out in order to focus on imperfect groupings.

B. Cluster Analysis (CA): apply a stopword list to the entire collection and check whether the imperfect groupings are optimized; identify a new list of writers whose works group at 100 MFW and then take them out in order to narrow the basin of imperfect groupings.

C. Bootstrap (consensus tree) & Cluster Analysis (CA): interrogate the collection for frequent groupings (100-1000 MFW) and determine the MFW thresholds for anonymity pools and genre solidarities.

D. PCA corr: apply random sampling and test more sensitive distances (Cosine Delta, Canberra) to anonymity pools (random sampling customize according to novel length either 500 or 1000)

COLLECTION of NOVELS
(general description)

Suggestions for a billion stylo “corpora”: subgroupings

LENGTH: 185 novels

Total wordcount: 8.678.907

Min – Max novel length: 208.773 (RosettiR_CuPalosul.txt) – 1.140 (CaselliD_Olteanca.txt)

Distribution: Short: > 20.000 (39 items), **Medium:** between 20.000 - 60.000 (101 items),
Long: 60000 (45 items)

PERIOD: 1850-1950 a.k.a. Modern Romanian Literature

Oldest – Youngest: 1853 (PelimonA_HotiiHagiul.txt) – 1939 (MatasaC_MovilaHaiducului.txt)

Time Slots (based on various moments of modernization):

T1: 1850 – 1862 (Transition Alphabet) = 9 items

T2: 1863 – 1882 (Centralization of Romanian Literary Institutions - official orthography) = 35 items

T3: 1883 – 1904 (Generalization of Phonological principale) = 81 items

T4: 1905 – 1939 (Modernization) = 60 items

SUBGENRE:

4 prominent subgenres:

a.hajduk (51)

b.historical (28)

c.mystery/ crime/ sensational (32)

d.sentimental (22)

PUBLICATION TYPE:

feuilleton vs. volume

complete vs. incomplete

finished vs. unfinished

Stopword list: preprocessing fixes & removing pronouns

- For some languages (EN, GER, POL, HUN, FR etc.), StyloR has a setting **for pronoun deletion**, but not for Romanian.

Preprocessing fixes:

1. Examining the file 'wordlist.txt' generated by StyloR, identifying most frequent typo errors, orthographical and phonological that needed normalization
2. Cleaning the collection with python scripts
3. Separating short-form pronouns from the compact constructions (e.g. "ducându-se" becomes „ducându” and „se”)
4. Generating a new 'wordlist.txt' with all pronouns long and short-form as individual entries
5. Cleaning the file 'wordlist.txt' generated by StyloR with '#examplepronoun' and adding other possible forms of Romanian pronouns.

Testing StyloR on Romanian novels: the pronoun conundrum

- Stylometry literature generally recommends the removal of pronouns on grounds that pronouns reveal the (narrative) viewpoint and not the author's individual style (Burrows 1987, 2002, Van Hulle & Kestemont 2016, Haverals et alii 2022, Karsdorp, Kestemont & Riddell 2022) vs. fewer studies on the relative importance of pronouns (Varela 2010, Pöpke et al. 2023)
- StyloR has a setting for pronoun culling – our comprehensive list could be useful to implement it for Romanian too :

Stylometry with R | stylo | set parameters

	INPUT & LANGUAGE	FEATURES	STATISTICS	SAMPLING	OUTPUT	
FEATURES:		words <input checked="" type="radio"/>	chars <input type="radio"/>	ngram size 1	preserve case <input type="checkbox"/>	
MFW SETTINGS:		Minimum 100	Maximum 100	Increment 100	Start at freq. rank 1	
CULLING:		Minimum 0	Maximum 0	Increment 20	List Cutoff 5000	Delete pronouns <input type="checkbox"/>
VARIOUS:		Existing frequencies <input type="checkbox"/>	Existing wordlist <input type="checkbox"/>	Select files manually <input type="checkbox"/>	List of files <input type="checkbox"/>	

OK

Hajduk subgenre tests

Classic Delta and Cosine Delta with and without pronouns

- Classic Delta and Cosine Delta without pronouns show **author clustering from a lower sill of MFW**, with an optimum clustering between 300 MFW and 500 MFW.

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/vizualizari_bune_fara_pronume_FINAL_16.11.23/RADH_CA_100_MFWs_Culled_0_Classic%20Delta_001.pdf => **100 Classic Delta MFW without pronouns**

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/vizualizari_bune_fara_pronume_FINAL_16.11.23/RADH_CA_100_MFWs_Culled_0_wurzburg_001.pdf => **100 MFW Cosine Delta without pronouns**

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/vizualizari_bune_cu_pronume_FINAL_16.11.23/Clasic/stylo_CA_100_MFWs_Culled_0_Classic%20Delta_001.pdf => **100 MFW Classic Delta with pronouns**

Subgenre Solidarity for the Hajduk Corpus with Classic Delta

- For 500 MFW with pronouns all the novels from HAI-RO corpus group in one big cluster

<https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/corpus%20style%20CA%20500%20MFWs%20Culled%200%20Classic%20Delta%20001.pdf>

- For 500 MFW without pronouns all the novels from HAI-RO do not cluster; instead there are groups that show a closer solidarity

<https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/corpus%20style%20CA%20500%20MFWs%20Culled%200%20Classic%20Delta%20001.pdf>

Subgenre Solidarity for the Hajduk Corpus with Cosine Delta

cf. Evert et. al. 2017 show that Cosine Delta distance is more stable in the results it produces for various settings

- From 500 to 900 MFW without pronouns, the novels form hajduk collection show a compact and stable solidarity.

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/RADH_CA_500_MFWs_Culled_0_wurzburg_001.pdf

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/RADH_CA_900_MFWs_Culled_0_wurzburg_001.pdf

Bootstrap Consensus Tree for the Hajduk Corpus

Subgenre Solidarity for the Sentimental Corpus

- From 700 to 900 MFW without pronouns, the novels labeled as sentimental in DCRR show a compact and stable solidarity.

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/sentimental/RADH_CA_700_MFWs_Culled_0_wurzburg_001.pdf

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/sentimental/RADH_CA_900_MFWs_Culled_0_wurzburg_001.pdf

Subgenre Solidarity for the Mystery/ Crime/ Sensational Corpus

- At 900 MFW without pronouns, the novels labeled as **Mystery/ Crime/ Sensational** in DCRR show a compact and stable solidarity.
- Thus, these subgenres should be treated as one label

Subgenre Solidarity for the Historical Corpus

- At 900 MFW without pronouns, the novels labeled as **Historical** in DCRR do not show a compact and stable solidarity.
- Thus, what is defined as historical novel is more heterogenous than **Hajduk**, **Mystery/ Crime/ Sensational** and **Sentimental** subgenres

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/istoric/RADH_CA_700_MFWs_Culled_0_wurzburg_001.pdf

Authorship attribution

Tests on 11 anonymous novels:

6 from the hajduk corpus

5 from a corpus of miscellaneous genres (sentimental, mystery/crime/sensational,
historical)

Hajduk anonymous novels

The 6 anonymous novels are grouped in the same cluster as N.D. Popescu's imitators

Visualizations WITH THE SERIES 'IANCU JIANU' BY N.D. POPESCU – a.k.a. the master of the genre and the epitome novel

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/corpus_explorari_haiducesti_CA_500_MFWs_Culled_0_Classic%20Delta_001finfin.pdf

Visualizations WITHOUT THE SERIES 'IANCU JIANU' BY N.D. POPESCU

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/corpus_explorari_haiducesti_CA_100_MFWs_Culled_0_Classic%20Delta_001.pdf

https://github.com/lucretiapascariu/RADHL/blob/main/corpus_explorari_haiducesti_CA_500_MFWs_Culled_0_Classic%20Delta_001.pdf

Anonymity pools, defined according to CA and bootstrap visualisations

After evaluating the results generated on the Hajduk corpus (51 texts), extracted from the entire collection (185 texts):

1. **PCA on random sampling (1000 words, 10 samples):** *Banditul Grozea* (Anonymous_BanditulGrozea.txt) vs. S. Stoenescu (StoenescuS_Corbea.txt), T. Stoenescu (StoenescuT_Dragusin.txt), Panait Macri (MacriP_HaiduculTandura.txt)
2. **PCA on random sampling (500 words because of novel length, 10 samples):** *Roșcan Haiducul* (Anonymous_RoscanHaiducul.txt) vs. P. Popescu (PopescuP_GrozaCataonilor(Fulger).txt) and PopescuP_VestitulBanditDragos.txt)
3. **To be determined:**

Codreanu Mare Haiduc National (Anonymous_CodreanuMareHaiducNational.txt) vs. N.D. Popescu (PopescuND_Miu.txt and other 12 Hajduk novels) vs. P. Popescu (PopescuP_GrozaCataonilor(Fulger).txt and PopescuP_VestitulBanditDragos.txt)

Ruxandra Haiduceasa (Anonymous_Ruxandra.txt) vs. C. Mătasă (MatasaC_MovilaHaiducului.txt) vs. Bucura Dumbravă (DumbravaB_Pandurul.txt, DumbravaB_Haiducul.txt) **a note for Bucura Dumbravă's novels = translations by Teodor Nica.**

Haiducul Jianul Lupul (Anonymous_HaiduculJianuLupul.txt) vs. G. Rădulescu-Niger (RadulescuN_Ropota.txt and other novels by the same author)

To be determined:

Anonymity pools should be also correlated with the timeslots of our collection

T1: 1850 – 1862 (Transition Alphabet)

T2: 1863 – 1882 (Centralization of Romanian Literary Institutions - official orthography)

T3: 1883 – 1904 (Generalization of Phonological principale)

T4: 1905 – 1939 (Modernization)

CASE 1.A.

Anonymous_BanditulGrozea.txt) vs. S. Stoenescu (StoenescuS_Corbea.txt), T. Stoenescu (StoenescuT_Dragusin.txt)

Parameters:

- ❖ mfw.min = 100
- ❖ mfw.max = 500
- ❖ mfw.incr = 200
- ❖ consensus.strength = 0.5
- ❖ distance.measure = "delta"
- ❖ sampling = "random.sampling"
- ❖ sample.size = 1000
- ❖ number.of.samples = 10

Result => *Banditul Grozea* belongs to another author

**300 and 500 MFW
Classic Delta
Without pronouns**

**Anonymous_BanditulGrozea.
txt
vs.
MacriP_HaiduculTandura.txt**

corpus stylo Cluster Analysis

300 MFW Culled @ 0%
Distance: wurzburg

corpus stylo Cluster Analysis

500 MFW Culled @ 0%
Distance: wurzburg

CASE 1.B.

Anonymous_BanditulGrozea.txt vs. MacriP_HaiduculTandura.txt

We added other novel written by Panait Macri tested two different distances ClassicDelta and Canberra.

**Classic DELTA =>
proximity**

- 500 MFW
- sample.size = 1000
- number.of.samples = 10

CASE 1.B.
Anonymous_BanditulGrozea.txt
vs. MacriP_HaiduculTandura.txt

Canberra => as testing
distance = almost
overlapping

300 MFW

- without pronouns
- most significant visualizations

Case 2

Anonymous_RoscanHaiducul.txt

vs.

PopescuP_GrozaCa and PopescuP_Vestit

analysis.type = "PCR"
consensus.strength = 0.5
distance.measure = "delta"
sampling =
"random.sampling"
sample.size = 500
number.of.samples = 10

Anonymity pools for miscellaneous genres

We removed the Hajduk novels from the entire collection of 185 novels

Cases of anonymity:

- 1. *PCA on random sampling (1000 words, 14 samples, Delta Classic):***
Anonymous_Oresbunare.txt vs. FundescuI_Scarlat.txt,
Ghica_UnBoemRoman.txt, AlexandruAl_Mistere.txt
- 2. *PCA on random sampling (1000 words, 10 samples, Canberra):***
Anonymous_Catastihulamorului.txt and Anonymous_Sobei.txt vs.
BolintineanuD_Manoil.txt vs. IonescuR_DonJuanii.txt
- 3. *To be determined:*** Anonymous_Mostenire.txt and Anonymous_Femeie.txt
vs. PopV_Americana.txt vs. NicolaescuWD_Triumful.txt

Case 1. Anonymous_Oresbunare.txt

Case 2. Anonymous_Catastihulamorului.txt and Anonymous_Sobei.txt

Grouped with D. Bolintineanu and Radu Ionescu, the latter being hypothesized as the author of two anonymous novels (Bălaeț 1974)

Case 2. Anonymous_Catastihulamorului.txt and Anonymous_Sobei.txt

Bolintineanu is closer to the anonymous novels

Case 2. Anonymous_Catastihulamorului.txt and Anonymous_Sobei.txt

RESULT = testing the idea of collaborative writing

OR

the two anonymous novels were written by the both authors (Ionescu + Bolintineanu)

OR

Manoil by Bolintineanu is co-authored with someone else (Radu Ionescu?)

OR

the author of the two anonymous novels is not in our collection

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Thanks!

